

yield for rice, but caused it to decline drastically in wheat planted in fine-textured soil, indicating that P release in fine-textured soils is adversely affected by CaCO₃ under dryland cropping.

Differences in P release may be caused by temperature and soil moisture conditions. Submerging the soil released the P due to CO₂ pressure by converting CaCO₃ to CaHCO₃ and H₂CO₃, which makes insoluble P soluble. Higher temperatures

Table 2. Olsen's extractable P related to temperature and period of submergence, Ludhiana, India.

Soil	Multiple regression equation	R value ^a
Loam	$y = 0.1064 x_1 + 0.7615^{**} x_2 - 0.0023 x_1 x_2 - 25.545$	0.89**
Sandy loam	$y = 0.314^{**} x_1 + 1.075^{**} x_2 - 0.00884^{**} x_1 x_2 - 35.961$	0.88**

^a**Significant at 1% level. y = Olsen's extractable P (ppm), x₁ = period of submergence (d), x₂ = av max soil temp (°C).

also increased P solubility. The effects of temperature and submergence are illustra-

ted by the multiple regression equations for loam and sandy loam soils in Table 2. □

Determining ammonium content in wetland soil extracts using an ammonia electrode

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We studied whether an ion-specific electrode could be used to determine the ammonium concentration in soil extracts, because the method is faster than conventional ones. We tested 1.0 N KCl extracts (soil:solution = 1:10) of 54 soil samples from 3 main rice growing areas of the Philippines – Maligaya, Cabuyao, and Iloilo.

Soil samples were taken 20 d after transplanting (DT). Ammonium concentration was measured with an ammonia electrode (Orion model 95-10) connected to a digital pH/mV meter calibrated for ammonium analysis. For low ammonium concentrations, the electrode was filled with a relatively dilute internal filling solution containing 5 mM NH₄Cl and 0.5 M NaNO₃. Sodium nitrate was added to inhibit osmotic interference. Instead of adding 1 ml of 10 M NaOH to 100ml

Relationship between indol-phenol blue method and ammonia electrode method of determining ammonium content of wetland soil extracts, IRRI.

of samples as indicated in the instruction manual to convert ammonium to ammonia, we added 2 ml of 0.25 M NaOH, which was enough to raise the pH above 11, as needed for the conversion.

To test the method's accuracy, aliquots

of the same soil extracts were analyzed by the Indolphenol blue method, a highly sensitive colorimetric method for detecting ammonium. The positive correlation between results of the two methods was highly significant (see figure). □

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Effect of rice straw mulching on wheat productivity

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broadcast wheat following deep water rice. Wheat seeds often are eaten by birds, germination tends to be low, and during later plant growth, particularly flowering, moisture stress reduces grain yield. Using straw mulch can reduce these problems. In 1982-83, we studied the effect of rice straw mulching in a farm trial at the Rainfed Deepwater Rice-based Cropping

Systems Research site in Daudkandi. Broadcast or line-seeded wheat was mulched with deep water rice straw. Although the field was not weeded, mulch substantially reduced weeds. Unmulched plots had to be weeded twice. Mulched wheat yielded 2.9-3.0 t/ha and gave a higher net return, irrespective of planting method (see table). Mulching conserved